

Studies on Arylacetamides. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(α -carbamoylarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl Sulphones

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Some new arylacetamide derivatives have been prepared bearing *p,p'*-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone moiety. *p,p'*-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone was condensed with different aldehydecyanohydrin to get the respective nitriles. The nitriles were then treated with concentrated sulphuric acid to get acetamide derivatives. The compounds were characterised by ir and pmr spectral data. The products were also screened for antimicrobial activity.

ACETAMIDE derivatives have been found to possess wide biological activities. Several reports have appeared in the literature, which highlight their chemistry and uses¹. The present communication deals with the preparation of some diarylacetamide of type (1) with an intention to synthesise better therapeutic agents.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone condensed with ethyl chloroacetate, was treated with hydrazine hydrate to get *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone. The hydrazide was condensed with different aldehydecyanohydrin to get the nitriles. The nitriles were then treated with concentrated sulphuric acid to get arylacetamide derivatives. The structural assignments of the products were based on their elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of the nitrile and amide derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method² at a concentration of 50 μ g using gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citreus*, gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serratia* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*. Activity of the compounds tested was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition.

The results showed that most of the compounds are moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (11–20 mm, zone of inhibition). The most active among the *p,p'*-bis(α -cyanoarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphones (Table 1; Sl. nos. 1–23) were those bearing

(alongwith zone of inhibition in mm) R = phenyl (Sl. nos. 18–26), cinnamyl (18–23), 4-chlorophenyl (20–22), 2,6-dichlorophenyl (18–23), 4-methoxyphenyl (19–23), 4-nitrophenyl (18–28) and 2-hydroxyphenyl (17–23). In case of *p,p'*-bis(α -carbamoylarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphones (Table 1; Sl. nos. 24–46) maximum activity was showed by those bearing R = 2-chlorophenyl (Sl. nos. 16–20), 2,4-dichlorophenyl (17–30), 2-methoxyphenyl (16–20), 4-methoxyphenyl (18–20), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (18–23), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (17–22), 4-nitrophenyl (16–20) and 2-hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl (19–20).

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DR-1_A 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

***p,p'*-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone:** An aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate (7 ml, 80%) was added to a suspension of *p,p'*-bis(carbomethoxymethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (8.45 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (15 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 h and cooled to room temperature. The hydrazide thus separated on cooling was crystallised from DMF, (6.85 g, 87%), m.p. 228° (Found: C, 48.77; H, 4.57; N, 14.14. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6N_4S$ requires: C, 48.72; H, 4.60; N, 14.20%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C–O–C str., asym.), 1 145, 1 290 (S=O str., asym. and sym. respectively), 3 300 (NH or NH₂ str.) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O str.); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 4.32 (4H, s, 2 $\times$ NH₂), 4.6 (4H, s, 2 $\times$ H₂COAr), 8.0–6.96 (8H, m, 2 $\times$ ArH) and 9.4 (2H, s, 2 $\times$ CONH).

***p,p'*-Bis(α -cyanoarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (Table 1; sl. no. 1):** To

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	N % : Found/(Calcd.)
<i>p,p'</i>-Bis(α-cyanoarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphones					
1.	Phenyl	158	79	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	18.41 (18.45)
2.	Cinnamyl	203	62	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.44 (12.42)
3.	2-Furyl	172	59	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	18.79 (18.90)
4.	2-Chlorophenyl	206	77	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.07 (12.12)
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	237	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.10 (12.12)
6.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	253	84	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.00 (11.02)
7.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	218	74	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.06 (11.02)
8.	2-Methoxyphenyl	254	66	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.22 (12.27)
9.	4-Methoxyphenyl	212	74	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.20 (12.27)
10.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	247	79	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	11.08 (11.28)
11.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	234	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	11.75 (11.72)
12.	4-Methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl	152	78	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	11.68 (11.72)
13.	2-Nitrophenyl	248	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	15.70 (15.68)
14.	3-Nitrophenyl	166	66	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	15.72 (15.68)
15.	4-Nitrophenyl	208	83	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	15.62 (15.68)
16.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	242	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.77 (12.80)
17.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	182	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.71 (12.80)
18.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	181	74	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	10.62 (10.58)
19.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl	168	68	C ₄₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.00 (11.10)
20.	2-Aminophenyl	196	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	17.13 (17.11)
21.	3-Aminophenyl	186	58	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	17.02 (17.11)
22.	4-Aminophenyl	188	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S	17.09 (17.11)
23.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	224	78	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S	15.68 (15.76)
<i>p,p'</i>-Bis(α-carbamoylarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphones					
24.	Phenyl	104	69	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	12.68 (12.72)
25.	Cinnamyl	156	59	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.69 (11.79)
26.	2-Furanyl	182	54	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	13.07 (13.12)
27.	2-Chlorophenyl	212	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.56 (11.52)
28.	4-Chlorophenyl	228	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	11.50 (11.52)
29.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	207	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	10.48 (10.52)
30.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	198	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	10.46 (10.52)
31.	2-Methoxyphenyl	251	61	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	11.60 (11.66)
32.	4-Methoxyphenyl	202	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	11.62 (11.66)
33.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	200	73	C ₂₆ H ₄₀ N ₂ O ₁₂ S	10.78 (10.76)
34.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	198	59	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₂ S	11.12 (11.16)
35.	4-Methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl	255	68	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₁₂ S	11.12 (11.16)

(Table 1 contd.)

36.	2-Nitrophenyl	122	69	$C_{12}H_{10}N_2O_4S$	14.89 (14.92)
37.	3-Nitrophenyl	214	73	$C_{12}H_{10}N_2O_4S$	14.87 (14.92)
38.	4-Nitrophenyl	186	77	$C_{12}H_{10}N_2O_4S$	14.96 (14.92)
39.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	189	69	$C_{12}H_{12}N_2O_4S$	12.03 (12.18)
40.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	193	78	$C_{12}H_{12}N_2O_4S$	12.08 (12.18)
41.	2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichlorophenyl	245	82	$C_{12}H_{10}Cl_2N_2O_4S$	10.10 (10.12)
42.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl	205	67	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_4S$	10.62 (10.60)
43.	2-Aminophenyl	186	62	$C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_4S$	16.18 (16.22)
44.	3-Aminophenyl	190	56	$C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_4S$	16.17 (16.22)
45.	4-Aminophenyl	136	71	$C_{12}H_{14}N_2O_4S$	16.28 (16.22)
46.	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	252	79	$C_{16}H_{22}N_2O_4S$	14.93 (15.00)

benzaldehyde (2.02 ml, 0.02 mol) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), potassium cyanide (13.02 g, 0.2 mol) dissolved in water (8 ml) was added followed by glacial acetic acid (12 ml). The mixture was then stirred for five minutes to form aldehyde cyanohydrin and kept at 0°. *p,p'*-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (3.94 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol was added to the reaction mixture, contents kept for 24 h at room temperature and poured in to ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (4.93 g, 79%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 61.47; H, 4.53; N, 13.41. $C_{22}H_{22}N_6O_6S$ requires : C, 61.52; H, 4.51; N, 13.45%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 230 (C-O-C str., asym.), 1 160, 1 290 (S=O str., asym. and sym. respectively), 1 665 (C=O str., amide-I sec.), 1 575 (NH def.+CN str., amide-II sec.), 1 200 (NH def.+CN str., amide-III sec.), 2 260 (C≡N str., very weak band) and 3 400 cm^{-1} (amine sec.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.78 (2H, s, 2×ArCH), 5.30 (4H, s, 2×ArOCH₂), 5.92–8.02 (18H, m, 2×ArH), 8.08 (2H, s, 2×CONHNH) and 11.52 (2H, d, 2×CONHNH, possibility of enolic OH also).

Similarly, other aromatic aldehydes were condensed with hydrazide (Table 1; sl. no. 1–23).

p,p'-Bis(α -carbamoylarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (Table 1; sl. no. 24): The *p,p'*-bis(α -cyanoarylmethylhydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenyl sulphone (3.12 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) at 5° and allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 h. The contents were poured into crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3:1), (2.28 g, 69%), m.p. 104° (Found : C, 58.15; H, 4.89; N, 12.68. $C_{22}H_{22}N_6O_6S$ requires : C, 58.18; H, 4.88; N, 12.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 250 (C-O-C str., asym.), 1 140, 1 290 (S=O str., asym.

and sym. respectively), 1 675 (C=O str., amide-I sec.), 1 540 (NH def.+CN str., amide-II sec.), 1 310 (NH def.+CN str., amide-III sec.), 1 675 (C=O str., amide-I prim.), 1 640 (NH def.+CN str., amide-II prim.), 1 410 (NH def.+CN str., amide-III prim.) and 3 400 cm^{-1} (NH or NH₂ str.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 3.86 (4H, s, 2×CONH₂), 4.78 (2H, s, 2×ArCH), 5.28 (4H, s, 2×ArOCH₂), 6.94–6.02 (18H, m, 4×ArH), 8.50 (2H, s, 2×CHNH), 8.70 (2H, s, 2×CONH) and 11.52 (2H, d, 2×OH enolic).

Similarly, other nitriles were converted to the corresponding arylacetamides (Table 1; sl. nos. 24–46).

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